

ESM I

Univariate Moderator Analysis

Cor	Heterogeneity Statistics				Moderator Analysis Results				
	τ^2	I^2	R^2	$Q_e(df, p)$	Variable	Estimate	SE	95% CI	p
HD	.005	64.25	48.81	81.73 (29, <.001)	intercept	-.17	.04	[-.25, -.10]	<.001***
					students	-.04	.05	[-.14, .06]	.42
					patients	-.08	.07	[-.21, .05]	.23
					translated DELTA	-.17	.06	[-.29, -.06]	<.01**
ED	.004	58.10	43.66	72.28 (29, <.001)	intercept	.21	.04	[.14, .28]	<.001***
					students	-.15	.05	[-.24, -.06]	<.01**
					patients	-.01	.06	[-.13, .12]	.93
					translated DELTA	.00	.06	[-.11, .12]	.97
XD	.004	61.35	45.69	82.20 (29, <.001)	intercept	-.21	.03	[-.28, -.14]	<.001***
					students	-.12	.05	[-.21, -.03]	<.01**
					patients	-.15	.06	[-.27, -.04]	<.01**
					translated DELTA	-.18	.06	[-.29, -.07]	<.001***
AD	.000	11.79	88.92	48.59 (29, .01)	intercept	-.14	.02	[-.18, -.09]	<.001***
					students	-.02	.03	[-.08, .04]	.55
					patients	.09	.05	[-.01, .19]	.07
					translated DELTA	-.13	.04	[-.21, -.05]	<.001***
CD	.006	58.34	44.45	73.72 (29, <.001)	intercept	-.20	.03	[-.26, -.13]	<.001***
					students	-.11	.05	[-.20, -.03]	.01*
					patients	-.11	.06	[-.23, .01]	.07
					translated DELTA	-.13	.06	[-.23, -.02]	.02*
OD	.014	82.94	5.23	151.08	intercept	.01	.05	[-.09, .12]	.79

Cor	Heterogeneity Statistics				Moderator Analysis Results				
	τ^2	I^2	R^2	$Q_e(df, p)$	Variable	Estimate	SE	95% CI	p
				(29, <.001)	students	.01	.07	[-.13, .15]	.92
					patients	-.09	.09	[-.27, .09]	.34
					translated DELTA	.04	.09	[-.14, .21]	.69

Note. Model intercept is either the correlation coefficient of the reference category in case of categorical moderators or the average correlation estimate in case of continuous moderators. All models were based on $k = 33$ studies. $Q_e(df, p)$ is the test of residual heterogeneity. Significance codes: * = $p < .05$; ** = $p < .01$; *** = $p < .001$.